

Configuration	A	B
Model Name	Intel i7-10700K	Intel Xeon Silver
Number of Cores	10	8
NUMA Nodes	1	1
L1 Cache	320KB	256KB
L2 Cache	10MB	2MB
L3 Cache	14MB	16MB